

Factors Leading the Failure of ICT Project Management in the Public Sectors in Tanzania

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Abstract:

The research study focuses on investigating the factors leading the failure of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) project management in the public sectors of Tanzania. The study utilizes a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. The research includes a comprehensive literature review to identify factors associated with previous ICT project failures. Interviews and surveys are conducted with key stakeholders involved in ICT project management in Tanzania's public sectors. The findings highlight various factors contributing to the failure of ICT project management, including

inadequate project planning and initiation, insufficient budget allocation, lack of skilled personnel, ineffective communication, and poor stakeholder engagement. Additionally, poor risk management strategies, organizational culture, political interference, and limited commitment from top management are identified as significant barriers to successful ICT project implementation. The implications of these findings emphasize the need for effective measures to address these challenges. Recommendations include improved project planning and initiation processes, increased budget allocation, enhanced human resource capabilities, and the establishment of effective communication channels. Creating a supportive organizational culture, minimizing political interference, and securing strong commitment from top management are also crucial to successful ICT project implementation in the public sectors of Tanzania. This research contributes valuable empirical evidence on the factors leading to ICT project management failure in Tanzania's public sectors. The findings can serve as a foundation for developing strategies and policies to promote successful ICT project implementation in similar contexts. Ultimately, addressing these challenges can lead to improved public service delivery and socio-economic development in the country.

Keywords: *Project Management, ICT Project, Public Sector.*

Introduction

Project management, which remains a new field compared to other related management sciences, is considered one of the fastest-growing areas in today's world (Meredith, Shafer & Mantel Jr, 2017). The Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK) Guide definition of project management is the "application" of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to project activities to meet the project requirements. Project management is accomplished through the application and integration of the forty-two logically grouped project management processes, which consist of five process groups: "initiating, planning, executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing." Failure to consider the fundamental concepts of project delivery can result in missed deadlines, overbudgeting, and costly changes, as well as frustration among project managers, team members, and other stakeholders (Meredith, Shafer & Mantel Jr, 2017). Without effective project management, projects often run into trouble and risk failure (Kerzner, 2017).

In the field of information and communication technology (ICT), project management has emerged as one of the most vital features of the overall IT development process. The key purpose of project management is to attest that projects are completed on time, within budget, within defined boundaries, and with the quality required to meet the goals of other projects (Samset & Volden, 2016). Information and communications technology projects are generally assumed to be just a set of activities demanding only hardware, networking systems, software, and applications with the end goal of introducing technological changes (Wu et al., 2018). Managing ICT projects is very difficult and requires good project management practices until the project is completed (Harrison & Lock, 2017).

Most ICT applications in the public sector of the least developed countries have partially or completely failed (Hua, 2022). One of the reasons given by the World Bank for failure is deficient project design and management (Ika, Diallo & Thuillier 2012). Another recent study

by (Choetkiertikul et al., 2017) found that after working with the University of Oxford for developed countries on around 5,400 large-scale IT projects, the problem of IT project management has grown in contrast to the dynamics of the field. The main findings quoted from the report consist of the following:

- 17% of large ICT projects fail so critically that they threaten the feasibility of the company
- On average, large ICT projects run 45% over budget and 7% overtime, yet deliver 56% less value than expected.

ICT is broadly adept in both private and public sector organizations, as evinced by the wide range of funding assigned to ICT (Obeidat & North, 2014). However, the ICT projects for the public sector are poorly managed and incompetent in achieving planned strategic goals and objectives. A study conducted by Standish Group from 2012 to 2018 showed that ICT projects in both the public and private sectors were not performing amazingly (Tereso et al., 2019).

A study done in Malaysia by (Vaheed, Tahir and Burhanuddin, 2015) established the factors that contributed to the failure of ICT projects. These factors include a poor business case, a lack of clear expected results, unfocused senior management on the project, poor communication, not properly engaging shareholders, conflicts of interest, bias in project evaluation, not seeing the big picture, and an unseen, narrow-minded decision maker. The question arises as to why ICT projects in the public sector around the world continue to fail, even after learning from and acknowledging past mistakes.

Much has been written about the extent and causes of ICT project failure, and most research has been conducted mainly in the public and private sectors of developed countries (Ashraf, Khattak & Zaidi, 2010). (Hosman & Arney, 2017) note that little research has been done in developing countries. Much has been written about the various socio-political, economic, and cultural reasons that information and

communication technology (ICT) cannot reach its potential in developing countries. Much less attention has been paid to the project, the technology, and the leadership itself and the role they play in ICT project failure (Kampermann et al., 2021). This study therefore focuses on the public sector in developing countries and the Tanzanian case study. Related research in this area focuses on the factors that influence the effective implementation of ICT projects in the Kenyan government (Muraya, 2015).

The successful implementation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) projects plays a crucial role in enhancing efficiency, transparency, and service delivery in the public sector of Tanzania (Lubua & Maharaj, 2012). However, numerous ICT projects in the public sector have experienced significant challenges and failures, resulting in wasted resources, delays, and the inability to achieve project objectives (Samsor, 2021). The failure rates of ICT projects in organizations have remained alarmingly high, indicating a persistent problem in project planning and implementation (Eden & Sedera, 2014; World Bank Group, 2011). Despite the availability of various ICT project management methodologies and standards, these projects often experience partial failures or complete abandonment, resulting in dissatisfaction among end-users and a failure to meet business needs (Kerzner, 2022).

Several studies have highlighted the prevalence of ICT project failures in different contexts. For instance, a global study by (Eden & Sedera, 2014) found that 35% of ICT projects in the public sector were classified as failures, while only 15% were considered successful. In New Zealand, a significant portion of public sector ICT projects experienced partial failures, with 59% falling into this category (Anthopoulos et al., 2016). Additionally, a World Bank study emphasized the high failure rates of ICT applications implemented in the public sectors of least developed countries (World Bank Group, 2011). These findings underscore the need to address the underlying factors contributing to the failure of ICT project management, particularly within the public sector in Tanzania.

Previous research has primarily focused on factors such as inadequate planning, management support, procurement issues, and change management, but limited attention has been given to investigating the dimensions of projects, technology, and leadership as potential contributors to the failure of ICT project management in the public sector (Eden & Sedera, 2014; World Bank Group, 2011). However, there is little research on the factors behind the failure of ICT project management practices in Tanzania's public sector. Using a representative sample of the Tanzanian public sector, this study examines the drivers of this failure in the context of existing trends and project management practices. Corresponding to this necessity, the present study conducted from three important institutions which are under the Ministry of Information, Communication, and Information Technology that are Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA), Tanzania Telecommunications Corporation (TTCL), and Information and Communication Technologies Commission (ICTC) offices are located in Dar es salaam region with the following objectives.

- To investigate the impact of technology issues on the failure of ICT project management in the public sector.
- To analyse the influence of leadership issues on the failure of ICT project management in the public sector.
- To develop a practical initiative aimed at overcoming ICT project failures in the public sector.

Materials and Methods

The study area for this research is Dar es Salaam region in Tanzania. This choice was based on the presence of key institutions relevant to the study, namely the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority (TCRA), Tanzania Telecommunications Corporation (TTCL), and Information and Communication Technologies Commission (ICTC). These institutions fall under the Ministry of Information,

Communication, and Information Technology (MICIT) and are directly involved in the implementation and management of ICT projects within the public sector in Tanzania. By focusing on these organizations, the researcher aims to gain insights into the challenges and factors contributing to the failure of ICT project management practices in the context of the public sector.

Population and Sampling Techniques

The study population consists of 160 ICT officials from TCRA, TTCL, and ICTC, who are directly and indirectly involved in the execution of public ICT projects in Tanzania. This includes ICT project managers, assistant ICT project managers, ICT external consultants, ICT internal experts/champions, and Project Management Office (PMO) staff members. To select the respondents, the researcher utilized both purposive sampling and simple random sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used to deliberately select individuals based on specific characteristics or criteria relevant to the research objectives. This method allowed the inclusion of experts, key informants, and individuals with specialized knowledge in the ICT field. On the other hand, simple random sampling ensured that every member of the population had an equal chance of being selected, providing a representative sample. The sample size was determined using Slovin's formula, resulting in a sample of 62 respondents. This size was considered sufficient to achieve meaningful results and insights for the study.

Sources and Tools of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized in this research. Primary data, which is original and fresh, was collected through interviews and questionnaires. Interviews allowed direct interaction between the researcher and the participants, enabling a deeper understanding of their perspectives. Questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from a larger sample size. For secondary data, document review was conducted, involving the examination of published books, journals, papers, and articles related to the research topic. Secondary data provided additional information

to support and complement the primary data collected through interviews and questionnaires.

Data Analysis

In this section, the researcher systematically applies statistical and logical techniques to describe and illustrate, condense and summarize, and evaluate data obtained from the survey conducted (Culbertson et al., 2012). Data analysis has two major prominent methods; qualitative research and quantitative research. Interviews for qualitative data, while questionnaires for quantitative data. The researcher used the content analysis technique to analyze qualitative data. This method focuses on interpreting and understanding verbal data collected through interviews and focus groups, and also provides an opportunity to quantify categories. Based on the objectives of this study, here's how the researcher perform content analysis step by step for each objective: Define the research objective the researcher clearly states that the objective, Select the data set that identify relevant sources such as academic papers, reports, case studies, or public sector documents that discuss ICT project failures in the public sector. Ensure the data set is representative and covers a range of ICT project management practices failure. Develop a coding scheme that captures different issues that can contribute to ICT project management practices failure. Code the data and apply the coding scheme to the selected data set and finally analyze the coded data, analyze the frequency and patterns of the identified issues. In this study, the computer data analysis software; IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was used to compute descriptive statistics, frequencies, and percentages of variables addressed from research objectives.

Results and Discussion

Technology Issues

The survey results revealed significant percentages of agreement among respondents regarding the influence of specific factors on project failure. Regarding technology issues,

80.6% agreed on the incompetence of project management practitioners, 85.5% agreed on the lack of project manager proficiency, and 88.7% agreed on the lack of project professionals as contributors to ICT project management failure. Additionally, 82.3% agreed on the lack of stakeholder involvement, 74.2% agreed on poor project communication management, and 72% agreed on the lack of teamwork and collaboration among project teams as factors influencing project failure in the public sector. Moreover, 85.4% agreed on the lack of understanding of project management fundamentals, 84.1% agreed on the usage of

inappropriate technology, and 79.3% agreed on the lack of stakeholders' awareness of project management as contributors to failure.

Interview responses from ICT project managers and assistant project managers further shed light on the factors leading to project failure. Poor ICT project leadership, political influences, lack of collaboration and cooperation among project teams, changes to IT infrastructure, and inadequate stakeholder participation were identified as significant factors contributing to project failure in the public sector.

Table 1. Technology Issues

	1	2	3	4	5
Incompetence of PM practitioners	9.5%	6.7%	3.2%	25.8%	54.8%
Lack of project manager proficiency	3.6%	9.7%	1.2%	29%	56.5%
Lack of project professionals	3.2%	4.8%	3.2%	30.6%	58.1%
lack of stakeholder involvement	6.8%	8.1%	2.8%	33.9%	48.4%
Lack of Project Communication management	8.1%	12.9%	4.8%	24.2%	50%
lack of teamwork and collaboration	1.6%	9.7%	16.1%	21%	51%
Lack of understanding of fundamentals of PM	4.8%	8.1%	3.2%	35.5%	48.4%
Usage of unappropriated technology	2.6%	4.8%	7.7%	29%	54.8%
Lack of stakeholders' awareness of PM	6.5%	3.2%	4.8%	24.2%	61.3%

Leadership Issues

The influence of leadership issues on the failure of ICT project management practices in the public sector. The statistical data presented in Table 4.7 demonstrates the respondents' agreement on various items related to the effect of leadership issues. According to the survey results, a significant percentage of respondents agreed that the absence of a long-term view (83.9%), lack of ICT project guidance (80.7%), and low commitment from top management (75.8%) contribute to the failure of ICT project management practices in the public sector. This suggests that poor leadership, management, and strategy formulation skills are prevalent in public sectors, greatly impacting the success of ICT projects. Furthermore, 92% of the respondents agreed that inflexible ICT policy hinders seamless ICT project management practices, ultimately leading to project failure. This highlights the need for public sectors to

recognize the dynamic nature of ICT and adapt ICT policies accordingly to leverage new technologies effectively.

In addition to the statistical data, insights from the interview responses shed light on specific leadership factors contributing to the failure of ICT project management practices in the public sector. These factors include the lack of support and commitment from top management, excessive bureaucracy in decision-making processes, and ineffective communication of the ICT strategy.

Interviewees emphasized that insufficient support and commitment from top management create obstacles in securing necessary resources and establishing clear project direction. Excessive bureaucracy in decision-making slows down processes and hampers timely action, hindering the project's ability to adapt and innovate. Furthermore, ineffective communication of the ICT strategy leads to

misalignment, confusion, and resistance to change among stakeholders, reducing engagement and support.

Table 2. Leadership Issues

	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Not Decided	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree
Absence of a long-term view	7.5%	2.5%	5.2%	25.8%	58.1%
Absence of ICT project guidance	4.8%	5.7%	13.7%	22.6%	53.2%
Low commitment from top management	1.6%	8.1%	9.7%	19.4%	61.3%
The inflexibility of ICT policies	1.2%	4.2%	2.6%	21%	71%

These findings indicate that addressing leadership issues, including securing top management support, streamlining decision-making processes, and improving communication strategies, is crucial for the successful implementation of ICT project management practices in the public sector.

Practical Initiative to Overcome ICT Project Failure

The practical initiative to overcome ICT project failure in the public sector in Tanzania. The practical initiative was divided into several factors: Project Management Factors, Top

Management Factors, Technology Factors, Organizational Factors, Complexity/Size Factors, and Process Factors. The statistical data presented in tables provided insights into the multicollinearity test and correlations among these factors. Multicollinearity is present when two or more predictors within a model are correlated and provide repetitive information about the response variable. It can be assessed using inflation variance and resistance factors (IFVs). If the VIF value surpasses 4.0 or the tolerance value falls below 0.2, it indicates the presence of multicollinearity, as suggested by (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 3. Tolerance and VIF Value for Independent Variables

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Project Management Factors	.553	1.809
	Top Management Factors	.332	3.015
	Technology Factors	.701	1.426
	Organizational Factors	.465	2.152
	Complexity/Size Factors	.629	1.589
	Process Factors	.302	3.312

According to the table, all items have a tolerance value greater than 0.20. Additionally, none of the items have a value exceeding 4. These findings suggest the absence of collinearity, indicating

that each item provides unique and non-redundant information. This further supports the notion that each item distinctly represents different aspects of the conceptual model.

Table 4. Regression analysis – Full Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.847 ^a	.717	.686	.34184

Predictors: (Constant), Process Factors, Project Management Factors, Complexity/Size Factors, Technology Factors, organizational Factors, Top Management Factors. This analysis contributes to our understanding of the relationship between project management factors, top management factors, technology factors, organizational factors, complexity/size factors, process factors, and ICT project failure. The data suggests that these independent variables collectively account for 84.7% of the

prediction of ICT project failure. The R square value indicates that there is significant variance in the dependent variable, implying that project management factors, top management factors, technology factors, organizational factors, complexity/size factors, and process factors play a role in ICT project failure. Since the minimum R square value should be above 30%, this model performs well and is suitable for further investigation.

Table 5. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.283	6	2.714	23.223	.000 ^b
	Residual	6.427	55	.117		
	Total	22.710	61			
a. Dependent Variable: Factors for ICT Project Implementation						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Process Factors, Complexity/Size Factors, Technology Factors, Project Management Factors, Organizational Factors, Top Management Factors						

The ANOVA Table 5 provides insights into the variance attributed to ICT project failure, utilizing Process Factors, Project Management Factors, Complexity/Size Factors, Technology Factors, Organizational Factors, and Top Management Factors. Out of the total variance of 22.710, the independent variables account for 16.283, while the remaining 6.427 is attributed to variables beyond the scope of this study. This finding further emphasizes the significant

explanatory power of the independent variables within the model when it comes to understanding ICT project failure. The regression coefficients and their statistical significance for each independent variable are presented in Table 6. The results reveal the magnitude and direction of the relationship between each predictor and the dependent variable, as well as their respective t-values and significance levels.

Table 6. Regression Analysis – Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.731	.346		2.111	.039
	Project Management Factors	.022	.074	.029	.303	.000
	Top Management Factors	.068	.112	.076	.607	.002
	Technology Factors	.064	.074	.075	.875	.015
	Organizational Factors	.125	.092	.143	1.356	.011
	Complexity/Size Factors	.111	.071	.141	1.556	.004
	Process Factors	.458	.111	.537	4.114	.000

The findings indicate that Process Factors ($\beta = 0.537$, $p = 0.000$), Project Management Factors ($\beta = 0.029$, $p = 0.000$), Complexity/Size Factors

($\beta = 0.141$, $p = 0.004$), Technology Factors ($\beta = 0.075$, $p = 0.015$), Organizational Factors ($\beta = 0.143$, $p = 0.011$), and Top Management Factors

($\beta = 0.076$, $p = 0.002$) all have statistically significant relationships with ICT project implementation in the public sector. These variables demonstrate positive relationships, indicating that higher scores on these factors are associated with a greater likelihood of successful ICT project implementation.

The regression analysis highlights the importance of considering Process Factors, Project Management Factors, Complexity/Size Factors, Technology Factors, Organizational Factors, and Top Management Factors in ensuring successful ICT project implementation in the public sector. These findings support the significance of these factors in influencing the outcome of ICT projects and suggest that addressing and prioritizing these areas can

enhance the likelihood of successful implementation in the public sector. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of considering multiple factors and adopting a holistic approach to overcome ICT project failure in the public sector. The findings highlight the importance of proper project management and decision-making in overcoming ICT project failure. Adequate risk management, user involvement, estimation of work, project planning, and skills and knowledge in project management are essential for successful project implementation. Additionally, competent decision-making in project selection and effective planning and follow-up by top management play crucial roles in project success.

Figure 1. A Model for Successful Implementation ICT Projects

A Model for Successful Implementation ICT Projects

The proposed model was derived by carefully running the regression analysis of the research variables and consideration of interview responses. Through considering and implementing these factors, public sectors in Tanzania can increase the likelihood of successful ICT project implementation, minimize the risk of failure, and achieve the desired outcomes and benefits. These project management factors from the designed model contribute to overcoming ICT project failures by addressing key areas of concern and ensuring a higher likelihood of project success. By incorporating these factors into project management practices, organizations can enhance their ability to overcome ICT project failures, increase project success rates, and deliver valuable solutions that meet user expectations and organizational objectives. Competence in making decisions on selecting ICT projects is a crucial top management factor that contributes to overcoming ICT project failures. When top management possesses the necessary competence in this area, they can effectively evaluate and select the most appropriate ICT projects for the organization.

The technology factors mentioned in the designed model contribute to overcoming ICT project failures by addressing key aspects related to the design, quality, compatibility, and availability of technology resources. Addressing these technology factors is crucial for overcoming ICT project failures. By aligning design and technology choices with current trends, ensuring high-quality end products, addressing compatibility issues, and providing sufficient hardware and software resources, organizations can mitigate risks, improve project outcomes, and deliver successful ICT solutions that meet user requirements and organizational objectives.

The organizational factors mentioned in the model contribute to overcoming ICT project failures by addressing key aspects related to project cost estimation, ICT project

management manpower, bureaucracy in the public sector, and resistance to system adaptation. Addressing these organizational factors is crucial for overcoming ICT project failures. By ensuring clear project cost estimation, having sufficient ICT project management manpower, reducing bureaucracy in the public sector, and addressing resistance to system adaptation, organizations can create an environment that supports successful ICT projects, minimizes risks, and maximizes project outcomes.

The complexity/size factors mentioned in the model contribute to overcoming ICT project failures by addressing challenges related to the scale, complexity, and expectations associated with large and complicated projects. By addressing these complexity/size factors, organizations can increase their chances of overcoming ICT project failures. By having the ability to handle large and complicated projects, organizations can effectively navigate through complexities and ensure project success. Furthermore, by managing the expectations of project champions, organizations can align goals and objectives with project realities, reducing the risk of failure due to unrealistic expectations.

The process factors mentioned in the model contribute to overcoming ICT project failures by focusing on critical stages of the project lifecycle and ensuring effective processes are in place. By incorporating these process factors into ICT projects, organizations can enhance their ability to overcome project failures. Proper feasibility studies, project selection processes, BPR processes, standardized methodologies, involvement of end-users, and effective communication contribute to successful project outcomes, improved stakeholder satisfaction, and the realization of expected benefits.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the failure of ICT project management practices in the public sector can be attributed to several technology-related issues. These include poor project

management practices, inexperienced project managers, and a shortage of project specialists. A lack of project communication management, teamwork, and collaboration within project teams also contribute to project failures. Technological challenges such as misinterpretations of client needs and the use of outdated legacy equipment further hinder successful ICT project management. Additionally, a lack of understanding of project management fundamentals, the use of inappropriate technology, and stakeholders' unawareness of project management also play a role in project failures.

The study identifies leadership issues as another factor contributing to ICT project management failures in the public sector. A lack of a long-term perspective, clear direction for ICT projects, and commitment from top management hinder successful project outcomes. Rigid ICT policies also impede effective project management practices, leading to project failures.

The study proposes several initiatives to overcome ICT project management failures in the public sector. Proper risk management, user involvement, and accurate task estimating are essential project management aspects that can prevent project failure. Ensuring compliance with contracts, having a well-defined project plan, possessing the necessary project management skills and expertise, and adequate background knowledge in ICT can also contribute to successful project outcomes.

On the technological front, providing the required hardware and software to interact with systems, avoiding compatibility issues between new and existing systems, and aligning design and technology with current trends can help overcome ICT project failures in the public sector.

Addressing organizational elements, clear project cost estimation, avoiding a shortage of ICT project management personnel, reducing excessive bureaucracy in public sector projects, and effectively handling resistance to new systems can lead to successful project management. Furthermore, proper vendor-user

communication during requirement gathering, appropriate project selection, conducting thorough feasibility studies, using standard methodologies, implementing Business Process Reengineering (BPR) processes, and involving end-users in user acceptance can all contribute to preventing ICT project failures in the public sector.

In summary, the study emphasizes the significance of addressing technology-related issues, leadership challenges, and implementing various initiatives to improve ICT project management practices in the public sector and prevent project failures. These insights can be valuable for policymakers and practitioners seeking to enhance project outcomes and overall efficiency in ICT project management.

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